

TO STUDY THE ADJUSTMENT PROBLEMS OF ADOLESCENCE IN RELATION TO EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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ABSTRACT

This research paper is an attempt to find the levels of emotional intelligence and adjustment among adolescents. The present study consisted of 100 samples equally divided into two groups (boys and girls) further these two groups are divided into two subgroups Rural and Urban. The tool was used for data collection An Adjustment inventory for school students developed by A.K.P. Singh and R.P Singh (1983). Mangal Emotional intelligence inventory developed by Dr.S.K.Mangal and Mrs.Shubra Mangal (1971).. Mean, S.D, Correlation and t-test were applied for data analysis. The results reveal that there is a significant positive relationship between adjustments of adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.

Key words: - Emotional intelligence, Adjustment, Gender.

Introduction:

Adolescence is known to be a period of exploratory self analysis and self evaluation ideally culminating in the establishment of a cohesive and integrative sense of self or identity. The search for identity by the social world, peers, parents, school and neighbourhood. Adolescence can be described as a phase of life beginning in biology and ending in society. Adolescence may be defined as the period within the life span when most of a person's biological, cognitive, psychological and social characteristics are changing from what is typically considered adult like. For the adolescent this period is a dramatic challenge are requiring adjustment to changes in the family, and in the peer group. Adolescence is a time of excitement and of anxiety; of happiness and of troubles; of discovery and of be wilderness; and of breaks with the future. Adolescence can be a confusing time-for the adolescent experiencing this phase of life, for the parents who are nurturing the adolescent during his or her progression through this period, and for other adults charged with enhancing the development of youth during this period. The hopes

challenges, fears and success of adolescent have been romanticised or dramatised in novels, short stories, and news articles. It is common place to survey a newstandand to find magazines articles describing the “stormy years” of adolescence, the new crazes or fades of youth or the explosion of problems with teenagers. Adolescents years to develop a unique and independent identity, separate from their parents; yes, they love their parents. But they don’t simply want to follow their steps. They challenge their parents in any way they can. They disobey their rules, criticize their “old fashioned” values; they discard their suggestions. They want that they should be respected and treated as adults. They can even offer useful insight on many things, and can set goals for themselves and follow them through. By this time, teenagers learn self regulation and accept social institutions and cultural traditions more easily. There can be mental and emotional problems. So during the period of adolescent the presence of emotional intelligence is very important because it is emotional intelligence which makes the individual to monitor one’s own another’s emotion.

Adjustment: - The term adjustment is often used as a synonym for accommodation and adaptation. Strictly speaking, the term denotes the results of equilibrium, which may be affect by either of these processes (Monroe, 1990). It is used to emphasize the individual’s struggle to along or survive in his or her social and physical environment. Good (1959) sates that adjustment is the process of finding and adopting modes of behaviour suitable to the environment or the changes in the environment. Shafer (1961) emphasized that adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs. Kulshrestha (1979) explained that the adjustment process is a way in which the individual attempts to deal with stress tensions, conflicts etc., and meet his or her needs. In this process, the individual also makes efforts to maintain harmonious relationships with the environment. In adjustment, the two crucial factors are the individual and the environment. In the study of the individual, the considerations are the heredity and biological factors, the psychological factors, and the quality of socialization given to him or her. Whereas, the environment includes all the social factors. Every individual from the time he or she steps out of the family and goes to school makes to a long series of adjustments between the whole unique personality and the environment. The ardent desire of each boy and girl to become an individual person having a healthy physique, a growing intellectual ability, a greater degree of emotional poise, and increased participation in social groups, such characteristics enhance one’s

personality. Even parents, teachers and other significant members of the society to which person belongs will encourage this desire.

Areas of Adjustment: - Adjustment in the case of individual consisted of personal as well as environmental components. These two aspects of adjustment can be further subdivided into smaller aspects of personal and environmental factors. Broadly speaking there are three areas where an individual needs to be adjusted to live balanced life. These are family home school and society.

Adjustment in family and home

An individual is not born adjusted or maladjusted. it is his Physical, Mental and emotional potentialities that are influenced and directed by the factors of environment in which he found himself adjusted or maladjusted. The family is the oldest and the most important of all the institutions that man has devised to regulate and integrate his behaviour as he strives to satisfy his basic needs. However, to understand the influence of the family on the child, it is important to understand the family and its functions .it has been confirmed through various studies that if family relationship has-been good, has been confirmed through various studies that if family relationship has been good, not only during childhood but also during adolescence, the person will develop into a well adjusted individual.

Adjustment at school: - The school is the major socialization institution for any child. It is the child's first contract with the world outside the house. School is one the most important foundation pillars on which the individual's personality develops. Children learn proficiencies in various abilities like, learning process and home work, social communications, handling emotion, and the management of day to day interactions at home and school. In reality, the growing child is dependent on the immediate environment i.e. the house and the school to meet his growth needs. The concern, therefore" extends to how the school facilities can be enhanced and improved to meet the growth needs of the children. Several studies have been reported in the area of social, educational, health and emotional adjustment of adolescents. Some studies try to relate adjustment with variables like intelligence, achievement, age, sex, socio-economic status, needs, anxiety, and security. Student's reaction to frustration has also been studied. A few studies focused on the nature, causes, and extent of indiscipline among students. The relation between

Tajinder K & Anita S / To Study the Adjustment Problems of Adolescence in Relation to Emotional Intelligence

indiscipline and variables like achievement, participation in co-curricular activities etc., were also examined. A review of the studies carried out in the three surveys of educational research edited by Buch (1991) reveals that no systematic attempt has yet been made to develop a tool for the assessment of adjustment problems of school students

Adjustment in society Adjustment is influenced by social maturity of the person. Maturity in social relationships means to establish good relations with family, neighbours, playmates, class fellows, teachers and other members of the society. Socially mature person behaves in accordance with social norms, customs and traditions.

Adjustment Problems of Adolescents: Adjustment problems of Adolescent Problems of Adolescence The physical and psychological characteristics of adolescents and the nature of developmental tasks which they are expected to perform often pose certain challenges and problems for adjustment. Basically adolescents face problems related to their home, school and society. They are presented in Table

Self related	Home related	School related	Society related
Body image Pimples Complexion Eating disorders Body changes Moodiness Touchiness Anger Hypersensitivity Feeling of rebel Crushes Infatuation Day dreams Personality	Authoritative parenting Poor rapport with parents Lack of communication Low socio-economic background Non conducive atmosphere Space constraint Comparison with others	Strict teachers Partial treatment Closed school atmosphere Not acceptable classmates Poor marks Too much homework No co- curricular participation. Long school hours	Gender bias, caste related problems Generation gap Orthodox practices Repressive atmosphere Over expectations Lack of friends

The problems listed in table are a few representative common problems which adolescents face. The more serious problems include drug addiction, alcoholism, smoking, truancy, sexual

obsessions, etc. They may not appear in everybody. There are variations in the experience of these problems across people.

Emotional intelligence: - Emotional intelligence (EI) is an ability, skill or, in the case of the trait EI model, a self-perceived ability to identify, assesses, and control the emotions of oneself, of others, and of groups. Various models and definitions have been proposed of which the ability and trait EI models are the most widely accepted in the scientific literature. Criticisms have centred on whether the construct is a real intelligence and whether it has incremental validity over IQ and the Big Five personality dimensions. The concept of emotional intelligence is a new one. No one can say exactly how much of the variability from person to person in life's course it accounts for but what data exists suggest it can be as powerful and at times more powerful, than I.Q. The concept of emotional intelligence taken together means, how intelligently we can control our emotions. Emotional intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves and for managing emotions well in us and in our relationships. Emotional intelligence (EI) is ability, skill or, in the case of the trait EI model, a self-perceived ability to identify, assesses, and controls the emotions of oneself, of others, and of groups. Various models and definitions have been proposed of which the ability and trait EI models are the most widely accepted in the scientific literature. Criticisms have centred on whether the construct is a real intelligence and whether it has incremental validity over IQ and the Big Five personality dimensions. The concept of emotional intelligence is a new one. No one can say exactly how much of the variability from person to person in life's course it accounts for but what data exists suggest it can be as powerful and at times more powerful, than I.Q. The concept of emotional intelligence taken together means, how intelligently we can control our emotions. Emotional intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves and for managing emotions well in us and in our relationships. Daniel Goleman (1998) for the first time developed a frame work of emotional competencies, which determines the extent of emotional intelligence acquired by an individual. This earlier frame work consisted of five domains or dimensions such as self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy and social skills. This was further refined by Richard Boyatzis, Goleman and Rhee in the year of 2000. Two more domains are added such as self-esteem and confidence,

interpersonal skills. Seven Basic Competencies of Emotional Intelligence Now Emotional Intelligence includes Seven basic emotional and social competencies:

1. Self-Awareness and Appraisal
2. Self-Regulation and Responsibility
3. Self- Motivation
4. Empathy and Acceptance of others
5. Social- Skills
6. Self-Esteem and confidence
7. Inter-Personal Relations

Reviews:

There exists a great deal of diversity in adolescents' level of maturity. Adulthood adolescents do exist (Galambos and Tilton Weaver, 2000). There have been enormous psychological pressures on adolescents to perform well and succeed in life. Emotional intelligence is positively correlated with appraisal of situation to be changed and problem-solving whereas threatened, lost, aggressive efforts and self criticism is negatively correlated with emotional intelligence among adolescents. (Tiwari and Verma 2008)

Another study conducted by Kim et al. (2003) suggested that negative life events experienced during early adolescence intensify the symptoms of sadness, fear and antisocial conduct which are domains for maladjustment in turn, increase risk for future adversities and life crises. The reciprocal process between negative life events and maladjustment has a developmental dynamic that unfolds in a more clear fashion across the years of adolescence. Smoking in adolescence is a great health concern as it is related to many chronic diseases and mortality in later life. It is also associated with high-risk behaviours among adolescents. School work is reported to be the most important factor which contributed to the stress among adolescents. Other common reasons reported for initiating smoking were curiosity, peer pressure, stress and addiction (Omar et al., 2007).

Khan and Asma (2012) conducted a study on emotional intelligence and academic achievement of children of working and non working mother and found that children of non working mother were more emotionally intelligent. Study indicated that mother separation from and absence to her children influenced the emotional intelligence to large extent.

Mohmood Ahmed Khan and Ahmed Bhat (2013) conducted a study on emotional intelligence on adolescence boy's and girl's. It had been found through the study that adolescent boys and girls

differed significantly on composite scale of their Emotional intelligence. Boys were found to have higher level of emotional intelligence than girls. Umadevi(2013) conducted a study on emotional intelligence of the adolescents and found that later born adolescents from joint families with large families possess high emotional intelligence skills.

Justification : most of the problems in our life, whether childhood problems, adolescent problems, home and family problems, work situation problems or political, regional or international problems are the results of misinterpretation of the involved sentiments, feelings and emotions of the concerned individuals, group of individuals, society and the nation. if proper efforts are made for training the emotions and developing proper emotional intelligence potential among the people right from their childhood, then it with right actions and behaviour on the part of the individual and group, to lead a better life in peace and cooperation. To progress and let other progress and to live and let others live are thus the ultimate goals of any education or training provided for developing one's potential of emotional intelligence. Keeping in view the importance of emotional intelligence in adjustment at various situations of life of an individual and especially in the life of adolescents, the present study has been undertaken by the researcher to study the adjustment of adolescents in relation to their emotional intelligence.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the relationship between adjustment of adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
2. To study the difference in adjustment of male adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
3. To study the difference in adjustment of female adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
4. To study the difference in adjustment of rural adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
5. To study the difference in adjustment of urban adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.

Hypothesis:

1. There would be no significant difference between adjustments problems of adolescent's students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
2. There would be no significant difference in adjustment of male adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
3. There would be no significant difference in adjustment adolescent female students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
4. There exists no significant difference in adjustment of rural adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.
5. There exists no significant difference in adjustment of urban adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence.

Research design

Method

Descriptive survey method was used for the present study.

Variables: -

- 1 Emotional intelligence
- 2 Adjustments
- 3 Gender

Sample: - The present study consisted of 100 students of Jammu district.

Tool used: - In the present study the investigator used the following tools.

1. An Adjustment inventory for school students developed by A.K.P. Singh and R.P Singh (1983).
2. Mangal Emotional intelligence inventory developed by Dr.S.K.Mangal and Mrs.Shubra Mangal (1971).

Data collection The data was collected from Govt higher secondary school Gandhi Nagar, Jammu and Govt higher secondary school Akhnoor Jammu.

Statistical techniques Used

Appropriate statistical techniques were utilized to analyse and interpret the data.

Results: - The present study aimed to study the levels of emotional intelligence and adjustment among adolescence. The obtained scores were assigned for different responses according to the item. Later these scores were arranged in tabular form than Mean, S.D., Correlation and t- test was applied for statistical analysis. Results are given in tables

Table 1: showing analysis of correlation between Adjustment and emotional intelligence among adolescence

Variables	N	Mean	S.D	Correlation	Remarks
Adjustment	100	30.63	9.13	0.34	Positive correlation
Emotional intelligence	100	34.5	14.81		

The results of the present study demonstrated that the mean scores of adjustment and emotional intelligence of adolescent students are 30.63 and 34.5, standard deviation 9.13 and 14.81, respectively and correlation is 0.34, which is not significant at 0.05 level. It indicated that, there is a significant positive relationship between adjustments of adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence. so, hypothesis-1 “there exists no significant relationship between adjustments of adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence

Table 2: showing Mean, S.D,Df and ‘t’value for mean scores of adjustment of male adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence

Male	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’-value	Remarks
Adjustment	50	29.98	7.88	1.26	Not significant at both levels
Emotional intelligence	50	32.86	13.82		

The mean scores of adjustment problems and emotional intelligence of male adolescent students are 29.98 and 32.86. The obtained ‘t’-value (1.26) which is less than table value at both

Tajinder K & Anita S / To Study the Adjustment Problems of Adolescence in Relation to Emotional Intelligence

levels(0.05 and0.01).it indicates that there exists no significant difference in adjustment of male adolescent and their emotional intelligence. This finding may be due to the fact that emotional intelligence has no effect on the adjustment of male adolescent students because all types of adjustment problems of adolescent students do not correlate with their emotional intelligence. These adjustment problems are created by other reasons as such, unhealthy environment at home and school, low understanding, low social-economic status of the parents’ etc.hence the second hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: showing Mean, S.D,Df and ‘t’value for mean scores of adjustment of female adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence

Female	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ -value	Remarks
Adjustment	50	31.32	9.27	1.92	Not significant at both levels
Emotional intelligence	50	36.18	15.32		

The mean scores of adjustment problems and emotional intelligence of female adolescent students are 31.32 and 36.18. The obtained‘t’-value (1.92) which is less than table value at both level (0.05and 0.01).it indicates that there exists no significant difference in adjustment of female adolescent students and their emotional intelligence. Thus our hypothesis “there exists no significant difference in adjustment of female adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence” is accepted.

Table 4: Showing Mean, S.D,Df and ‘t’value for mean scores of adjustment of Rural adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence

Rural	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ -value	Remarks
Adjustment	50	28.52	7.75	2.19	Not significant at0.01 level
Emotional intelligence	50	35.14	13.72		

Our fourth hypothesis “There exists no significant difference in adjustment of rural adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence”. The mean scores of adjustment problems and emotional intelligence of rural adolescents are 28.52 and 35.14.The obtained‘t’ values(2.19) which is less than the corresponding tableat0.01 level significance. it means there exists no

significant difference in adjustment of rural adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence

Table 5: Showing Mean, S.D, Df and ‘t’value for mean scores of adjustment of Urban adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence

Urban	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ -value	Remarks
Adjustment	50	34.78	8.72	0.36	Not significant at both level
Emotional intelligence	50	33.86	15.80		

To verify hypothesis-5 “There exists no significant difference in adjustment of urban adolescent students in relation to their emotional intelligence” the mean scores of adjustment problems and emotional intelligence of urban adolescents are 34.78 and 33.86. The obtained ‘t’-value (0.36) is less than table value at both level (0.05 and 0.01) it indicates that there exists no significant difference in adjustment of female adolescent students and their emotional intelligence. This finding may be due to the facts that emotional intelligence has no effect on the adjustment of urban adolescent students because all type of adjustment problems of adolescent students do not correlated with their emotional intelligence. The adjustment problems are created by other reasons as such unhealthy environment at home and school, low understanding, low socio economic status of the parent’s etc. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion:

To conclude the present study demonstrated that adjustment of adolescent students and their emotional intelligence are positively correlated. It means that emotional intelligence of adolescent students has effect on their adjustment. There is a great need to explore the awareness about the Emotional Intelligence. Emotional Intelligent people are more likely to succeed in everything they undertake. Quality emotions and feeling help student give their best potential in the classroom. The inclusion of emotional intelligence as part of curriculum could lead to

variety of positive personal and social outcomes. Increasing emotional intelligence may not only facilitate the learning process and improve carrier choice and likelihood success, but could also enhance the probability of better personal and social adaptation.

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